

Microstructure and Fracture Behaviour of Unidirectionally Reinforced Carbon Fiber/Carbon Composites

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ABSTRACT

The carbon matrices were prepared from pyrolysis of thermo-setting resin(GC) and CVD carbon (CVD). The fibers used were of high strength (HS CF) and high modulus (HM CF) carbon fibers. The CF/GC composite with heat treatment temperature of below 1000°C showed a brittle fracture; on the other hand, the composite heat treated to above 2000°C showed pseudo-plastic fracture. The transition temperature from brittle to pseudo-plastic depended on the fiber used. The fracture pattern was affected by the contents of graphite structure. The CF/CVD C composite of isotropic carbon matrix showed a brittle fracture. However, the composite of smooth columnar carbon matrix showed pseudo-plastic fracture pattern caused by the presence of annular cracks around the fiber. Fracture behavior at high temperature was similar to that at ambient temperature. The strength at 1400°C was higher by 10-15% as compared to that at ambient temperature, and the Young's modulus of HM CF/GC composite by 40 %.

1. INTRODUCTION

High performance carbon fiber reinforced carbon material (C/C composite) is now being developed vigorously, in accordance with the development of high strength high modulus carbon fiber and to effect the application of the carbon fiber economically, especially in the field of space engineering. The development of C/C composite needs a detailed characterization of variables: microstructure and fiber-matrix interface, which affects the mechanical properties. But these variables are complex functions of the constituent carbon materials and the fabrication process. Besides the mechanical properties at ambient temperature, high temperature strength is also of great relevance for applications under severe environments.

For the present work, unidirectionally fiber reinforced C/C composites were used. Different types of matrices were obtained by two processes: (1) the pyrolysis of thermo-setting resin which upon carbonization generally yielded glass-like carbon and (2) chemical vapor deposition of carbon(CVD) by the pyrolysis of propane at high temperatures. This paper deals with the influence of microstructure on mechanical properties (fracture behaviour, Young's modulus and strength) of the composite at both ambient and high temperature.

2. EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

2-1. SPECIMENS

The carbon fibers used here were Torayca T-300 (high strength type, HS) and Torayca M-40 (high modulus type, HM) both of which were PAN based carbon fibers.

(a). CF/GC COMPOSITES

Bundles of the fibers were dipped and aligned unidirectionally in the furfuryl alcohol condensate, and then these were carbonized by heating at 1000°C for one hour. The composites were composed of 50 vol % of fiber fraction in furan resin matrix. Heat treatment of the specimens were conducted at a heat treatment temperature (HTT) between 1000°-3000°C for one hour in Graphite resistance tube furnace. The precise fabrication procedure is reported elsewhere [1].

(b). CF/CVD C COMPOSITE

Carbon fibers were unidirectionally aligned in Graphite reaction cylinder, which was induction heated (400 KHz, 7 KW) between 1200°-1400°C. After equilibration for one hour at prescribed temperature, a gas mixture of hydrogen (H₂) and propane (C₃H₈) was introduced into the reaction cylinder. The detailed fabrication procedure is also reported elsewhere [2].

2-2. MEASUREMENT OF MECHANICAL PROPERTIES

The composites were cut along the fiber axis (60 mm in length) to produce samples of 10mm x 3mm in cross section. Flexural strength perpendicular to the fiber axis were determined by four point bending test. Inner and outer spans between the applied loads were 13.5mm and 40mm, respectively. Notched bend specimens were also used to avoid cracks at the contact point of stressing edges. The notch was machined by a diamond blade (0.25 mm width) at the center of the specimen, perpendicular to the fiber axis to initiate a crack at the middle of the tension side of the composite. The bend specimens were loaded with a constant crosshead speed of 0.1mm/min in a testing machine (Autograph 25T). Young's modulus was measured from the stress strain relations. High temperature strength was measured with the same size specimen, which was set in a specially made bending apparatus in a high temperature furnace attached to the testing machine.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

3-1. MICROSTRUCTURE OF CF/GC COMPOSITES

An anisotropic region appeared in the matrix around the fiber after the heat treatment above 1000°C, and this was of glass-like carbon (Fig.1-a). The anisotropy of GC derived from accumulated stress at the fiber/matrix interface of the order of 4 Kbar during the carbonization process. The anisotropic region changed to graphite layer structure in accordance with HTT above 2000°C. From the microstructural observation, the graphite started appearing from the matrix near the fibers, aligning the c-axis perpendicular to the fiber axis from 2000°C, as shown in Fig.1-b,c. With the increase of HTT, the area of the graphite structure region increased. The C₁ spacing decreased from 6.9 to 6.73Å, the graphite layer thickness (L_c) grew and also bulk density increased from 1.55 to 1.70 gr/cm³ after the heat treatment between 2000° and 3000°C [1,3].

In the high modulus fiber composite (HM CF/GC composite), the graphite appearance temperature shifted to lower temperature (~1400°C) compared with that of the high strength fiber composite (~2000°C, HS CF/GC composite), as shown in Fig.2-a. In addition to it, the C₁ spacing of HM CF/GC composite was smaller and L_c was larger than those of HS CF/GC composite at the same HTT. The phenomena would depend on the higher stress accumulation in the HM CF/GC composite, because of the higher Young's modulus of the HM fiber than that of the HS fiber. The shape of the fiber in the HM CF/GC composite remained at the original fiber shape after the heat treatment at above 2800°C. However, the shape in the HS CF/GC composite was distorted at above 2800°C as can be seen in Figs.1-c and 2-c.

3-2. MICROSTRUCTURE OF CF/CVD C COMPOSITE

The microstructure of the CVD carbon varied according to the temperature and the partial pressure of C₃H₈. At lower partial pressure and higher deposition temperature of C₃H₈, the CVD carbon consisted of fine grains which were too small to resolve optically. This microstructure was classified as isotropic carbon (ISD) as shown in Fig.3-a. At the intermediate temperature and intermediate partial pressure the CVD carbon consisted of roughly oriented anisotropic carbon which showed columnar structure (RC) as shown in Fig.3-b. At lower temperature and higher partial pressure, the CVD carbon consisted of smoothly oriented columnar structure (SC) adjacent to the RC carbon around the fiber (Fig.3-c). The uniqueness of the SC carbon matrix composite was circular cracks seen around the fibers in the matrix.

3-3. FRACTURE BEHAVIOUR OF CF/GC COMPOSITES

Typical stress-strain curves for HS CF/GC composite is illustrated in Fig.4. The composite heat treated at 1000°, 2000° and 2400°C behaved in a brittle manner and those heat treated at above 2600°C showed a pseudo-plastic fracture behavior. In the latter composites, a delamination of matrix and fiber pull-out were observed. Fig.5 shows the stress strain curves for HM CF/GC composite.

The HM CF/GC composite heat treated at above 2000°C behaved in a pseudo-plastic manner. From brittle to pseudo-plastic fracture, the transition temperature shifted to lower temperature with the application of high modulus fiber.

The four point bending strength of HS CF/GC composite is shown in Fig.6 by triangles as a function of HTT. High strength was obtained in a Graphite composite. The strength reaches a maximum value of 450 MN/m² at about 2400°C HTT, and then decreases with increasing HTT. The strength of HM CF/GC composite is also shown in Fig.7 with closed squares. The strength reaches a maximum value of 520 MN/m² at about 2600°C HTT. The strength of the HM fiber is lower than that of HS fiber. However, the maximum strength of the HM CF/GC composite was higher than that of the HS CF/GC composite. The HS fiber and the HM fiber were alone heat treated at about 1400°C and 2800°C respectively. The stability of HM fiber was better than that of HS fiber. This is confirmed by the microstructural changes shown in figures 1-c and 2-c. Accordingly, the strength of the HS fiber decreased by the heat treatment above 2000°C, and the strength of the HM fiber was maintained after the heat treatment below 2800°C.

It should be noted that in the composites heat treated at 2600° and 2800°C, fracture did not initiate on the specimen surface between inner load points, but started initially at the contact point due to local cracks. It is inferred that the stress degradations in the composites treated at higher temperature is due to cracks caused by the predominantly anisotropic property of the composite. For this reason, four point bending tests were performed on the notched beams. The fracture manner of notched beam for HS CF/GC composite are shown in Fig.7 and the strength are shown by open circles in Fig.6. In this case, fracture initiated at the notch front and proceeded parallel to the applied stress axis, macroscopically. Strength of the notched specimens were smaller than that of the un-notched specimens, but increased monotoniously with the heat treatment temperature. This change in strength coincides with the Graphitization of the matrix, which seems to be an intrinsic mechanical property.

SEM observations were used to further characterize the fracture behaviours. SEM views of the fracture surface illustrating the fiber pull-out, and the cleaving or the delamination of the matrix is shown in Fig 8. Fig.8-a is a fractograph of the composite heat treated at 1000°C. It reveals the smooth fractured surface which opens perpendicular to the fiber axis. The crack seems to propagate in the matrix thus cutting the fibers on the cleaved surface. This composite exhibited brittle fracture with a low strength of about 100 MN/m². Fig.8-b shows the fracture surface of the composite heat treated at 2400°C. Pull-out of fiber bundles are seen, but the fractured surfaces of matrix appear relatively smooth. In this composite, the matrix was partially graphitized along the fiber. The pull-out of fiber bundles are due to delaminations at the fiber-matrix interface and/or at the interfaces of the glass-like carbon and graphite in the matrix.

Fig.8-c shows the fracture surface of the composite heat treated at 2800°C. The matrix changed to graphite structure. The fracture surface is of fibrous nature with long fiber pull-outs. The crack does not propagate perpendicular to the fiber axis but runs parallel to the relatively weak interface between fibers and matrix. The debonding of the interfaces probably blunted the crack tip, which lead to the high strength in this composite.

3-4. FRACTURE BEHAVIOUR OF CF/CVD C COMPOSITE

Two types of composites with different matrix microstructures were tested. These were an ISO+RC carbon composite and two RC+SC carbon composites. The stress strain curves measured by the four-point bending test are shown in Fig.9. As shown in this figure, there are two types of fracture patterns. One displays an extremely sharp decrease in stress after maximum stress (ISO+RC matrix); in the other, the stress is maintained at about 60 % of maximum stress in spite of the large strain, which indicates high fracture energy and toughness. The form of these patterns did not depend on the fiber content of the composites. In-situ observation showed that the fibers were fractured near the surface of maximum stress, which was confirmed with acoustic emission in the ISO+RC composite.

The fractured surfaces of ISO+RC and RC+SC composites were observed by SEM (Fig.10). Fig.10-a shows that ISO carbon adhered to fibers well, and the cracks propagated in the RC carbon matrix, then runs through the boundary of RC carbons to a weak point in another fiber. No fiber pull-out was observed in the fractured ISO+RC composite. Tentative measurements of the shear strength of the matrix by compression testing showed higher values of strength for the ISO+RC matrix than that for RC+SC matrix. As a result of this, cracks which initiated in the RC carbon matrix propagated in directions perpendicular to the fiber axis.

In case of RC+SC composites, fiber fracture was not observed until 1% strain, but delamination parallel to the fiber axis was observed at the region of maximum shear stress. It was also observed that the cracks run entirely through the SC carbon matrix in the fractured RC+SC composite, as shown in Fig.9-b. As shown in Fig.3-c, many cracks exist in the as-deposited SC carbon, in annular rings around the fibers.

3-5. HIGH TEMPERATURE STRENGTH OF CF/GC COMPOSITES

High temperature strength of CF/GC composites were measured at 1000°C and 1400°C. A typical stress strain curves are shown in Fig.11. The fracture manner of both HS CF/GC and HM CF/GC composites at high temperature was the same as that of at ambient temperature. However, the strength increased with increasing the temperature as shown in Fig.12. The high temperature strength at 1400°C increased by 10-15% as compared to that at ambient temperature. The amount of increasing strength was the same for all of the CF/GC composite. The increase of strength with increasing temperature corresponds to the behavior of that for graphite materials. The Young's modulus of HM CF/GC composite with HTT of 2600°C increased by 40 % at 1400°C as compared to that at ambient temperature; on the other hand, the Young's modulus of HM CF/GC composite with HTT of 1000°C increased up to 1000°C, but decreased above 1000°C as shown in Fig.12. The Young's modulus of HS CF/GC composite decreased above 1000°C even when heat-treated to 2000°C. The fall-in of Young's modulus for HS CF/GC composite is still in question to be analyzed. The high temperature strength of CF/CVD C composite will be reported later.

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(a) HTT 1000°C (b) HTT 2000°C (c) HTT 2800°C

Fig. 1. Microstructures of HS CF/GC composite under crossed nicols.

(a) HTT 1400°C (b) HTT 2800°C (c) HTT 3000°C

Fig. 2. Microstructures of HM CF/GC composite under crossed nicols.

(a) Isotropic (ISO) (b) Rough Columnar (RC) (c) Smooth Columnar (SC)

Fig. 3. Microstructures of CF/CVD C composite.

Fig.7. Load-deflection curves for notched HS CF/GC composite with various HTT.

Fig. 8. Fractured surfaces of HS CF/GC composite.

Fig.9. Stress-strain curves for CF/CVD C composite with various structure of matrix by four point bending test.

Fig.4. Stress-deflection curves for HS CF/GC composite with various HTT by four point bending test.

Fig.5. Stress-strain curves for HM CF/GC composite with various HTT by four point bending test.

Fig. 6. Four point bending strength vs HTT for HS CF/GC composite, HM CF/GC composite and notched HS CF/GC composite.

Fig.10. Fractured surfaces of CF/CVD C composite.

Fig.11. Stress-deflection curves for HM CF/GC composite with various HTT by four point bending test at high temperature.

Fig.12. High temperature strength and Young's modulus for HS CF/GC and HM CF/GC composite with various HTT.